

Mapping St James' Hospital data to the DeepMind acute kidney prediction algorithm

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The full set of 1,467 data fields are collected as fixed predictors (that is, baseline variables) and time-varying predictors (that is, variables measured on a repeated basis during a hospitalization).

Fixed predictors included:

Age; was top coded at 89 years.

Height; calculated as the mean value from the 3 years preceding admission for VA patients, and the most recent value within the past year for UM patients. If no recent value was identified for UM patients, the first inpatient measurement was used.

Weight; calculated as the mean value from the 3 years preceding admission for VA patients, and the most recent value within the past year for UM patients. If no recent value was identified for UM patients, the first inpatient measurement was used.

Body Mass Index was calculated using the baseline height and baseline weight.

- **17 following comorbidities** were calculated with the Charlson comorbidity index using data from 1 year before admission for VA from the current encounter for UM patients.

Myocardial Infarction

Congestive Heart failure

Peripheral Vascular Disease

Cerebrovascular Disease

Chronic Pulmonary Disease

Dementia

Paralysis

Diabetes Complicated

Diabetes Uncomplicated

Kidney Disease

Mild Liver Disease

Mod Severe Liver Disease

Peptic Ulcer Disease

Rheumatic Disease

Metastatic Cancer

Non-Metastatic Cancer

HIV AIDS

- **Admission to a Surgical Service**, which is captured at the time of admission.
- **Intensive Care Unit Status**, which is captured at the time of admission and
- **Baseline Serum Creatinine (SCr)**, was determined by the following order of preference:
 1. mean outpatient SCr between 7 and 365 days before admission and

- within 7 days before admission,
- 2. first inpatient SCr test for VA patients or first documented SCr value within 24 hours of admission for UM patients.

Time-varying predictors consist of:

- **Eight vital signs** were pulled regardless of the frequency of measurement.

Inpatient Weight

Systolic Blood Pressure

Diastolic Blood Pressure

Respiratory Rate

Temperature

Pulse

Blood Oxygen Level

Central Venous Pressure

- Twenty-six laboratory testing components as follows were selected due to universal use across different health systems.

Serum Albumin

Alkaline Phosphatase

Alanine Aminotransferase

Aspartate Transaminase

Total And Direct Bilirubin

Blood Urea Nitrogen

Serum Calcium

Carbon Dioxide

Serum Chloride

Serum Glucose

High-Density Lipoprotein

Cholesterol

Haematocrit

Haemoglobin A1c

Haemoglobin

International Normalized Ratio

Low-Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol

Microalbumin-To-Creatinine Ratio

Serum Phosphate

Platelet Count

Serum Potassium

Serum Creatinine (SCr)

Serum Sodium

Total Cholesterol

Triglyceride

Total White Blood Cell

- Administration of following 11 drug classes is examined as opposed to individual medications:

Aminoglycosides

Sympathomimetics

Beta Blockers

Alpha Blockers

Calcium Channel Blockers

Antilipemic Agents

Non-Salicylate Antirheumatic Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory drugs

Loop Diuretics

Angiotensin-Converting Enzyme

Inhibitors

Angiotensin II Inhibitors

Non-Ionic Contrast Media

Patient states captured at 6 hours intervals beginning with the time of admission for each patient. For each 6 hours interval, summary statistics (length, minimum, mean, median, maximum) were calculated for the preceding 48 hours divided into 6 hours windows for vital signs and laboratory test results.

$$5 \text{ Statistics summary} * (48/6) \text{ time windows} * (26 + 8)$$

Using these summary statistics, additional variables were created based on clinical relevance: **the ratio of the most recent maximum SCr to baseline SCr, the difference between the most recent maximum SCr and baseline SCr, and the ratio of most recent maximum blood urea nitrogen to most recent maximum SCr.**

Medication states captured at 24 hours intervals beginning with the time of admission and truncated at 7 days of hospitalisation:

$$11 \text{ drug classes} * 7 \text{ interval of 24 hours}$$

Exploring the Data of St James' Hospital (SJH)

Two set of data has been shared with us so far as follows:

1. Code catalogue of all data codes available in EPR system of SJH, which has been shared as **5 CSV files** as follows :

CSV File Name	No. Of Records	No. of Fields
DW_EPR_SERVICE_CODES	3725	51
EPR_CODES	251890	29
EPR_FORM_CODES	591	22
EPR_IVIEW_CODES	1771	6
EPR_ORDER_CATALOGUE_CODES	14009	65

2. EPR data of a sample patient in the cohort of study , which has been shared as **4 CSV files** as follows :

CSV File Name	No. Of Records	No. of Fields
MRN_311781_EPR_CLINICAL_EVENT_20240216	28343	74
MRN_311781_EPR_ENCOUNTER_20240216	236	147
MRN_311781_EPR_ORDERS_20240216	2916	119
MRN_311781_EPR_ORDERS_DETAILS_20240216	34976	119

To evaluate the performance of the sample model on the local EPR data of SJH, we need to train the sample model on the same data fields (features) of the patient cohort.

Therefore, we need to be sure that the same data fields are available in SJH's EPR system and then extract and retrieve the patient's records for those fields from SJH's Cerner system. Therefore, a comprehensive search was conducted using exact and fuzzy matching for all the fixed predictors of sample models with data field codes in the code catalogue. Still, we have encountered common patterns of redundancy in this matching, which can happen due to a lack of contextual domain knowledge of the secondary researcher (me), a lack or shallow level of normalization in SJH's data model and or a lack or low level of data harmonisation and standardisation in the data fields of SJH's EPR system.

Some examples of these patterns are as follows:

- **“Age”** appeared in more than 30 unique code records in SJH’s code catalogues
- There are several unique codes for mapping **“Sex”** in SJH’s code catalogues either with term of **“sex”** or **“gender”**
- Different matches has been found for **“Myocardial Infarction”** as :
 - **“Acute or Recent Myocardial Infarction”**
 - **“Emerg. Med - Myocardial Infarction”**
 - **“Acute Myocardial Infarction”**
 - **“Myocardial Infarction”**
 - **“Myocardial Infarction [Hx of Remote]”**
 - **“Remote Myocardial Infarction”**
- There are several matching redundancies in SJH for abbreviation of a data code and its extended name, for example:
 - **“Acute Myocardial Infarction” and “AMI”**
 - **“Congestive Heart Failure” and “CHF”**
 - **“Human Immunodeficiency Virus” and “HIV”**
- There are some predictors in sample model which are very ambiguate or very general for matching, for example:
 - **“Kidney Disease”**
 - **“Mild Liver Disease”**
 - **“Diabetes Mellitus, complicated”**
- Some matched data codes in SJH’ has more detailed conditions, such as:
 - **“Systolic Blood Pressure”** which can be matched with **“ Systolic Blood Pressure Sitting” or “Systolic Blood Pressure Standing”**